

Numerical Modelling and Analysis of Earthquake Resistant Houses Built Using Interlocking Adobe Mud Blocks

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Abstract Unburnt earthen houses are recognized to be the preferred choice of low cost living solution for economically challenged population in most of the developing and under-developed countries. Several key factors such as ease of availability of local materials, economic and environmental-friendly construction, simplified construction methodology, and comfort of living during various weathered condition, etc encouraged the local people to construct such houses. Overall, earthen houses offer an alternative approach towards sustainable building solution with low carbon footprint. The present study delves into the realm of earthen construction, examining the structural resilience of traditional mud or adobe structures through an interlocking block system. The study involves modelling of a representative wall within ABAQUS environment. The Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model is employed to accurately simulate block material behaviour, highlighting its adaptability in representing tensile and compressive responses. The static load-displacement behaviour reveals crucial insights into the model wall's performance. The findings contribute to a nuanced understanding of interlocking block systems, offering a foundation for design improvements and potential applications in enhancing the structural integrity of earthen constructions. This research serves as a significant stride towards resilient and sustainable solutions in the field of earthen construction practices.

Keywords Earthen Houses, Interlocking Blocks, ABAQUS, CDP.

Introduction

Earthen construction, also known as mud construction or adobe construction has a rich history in India and remains a prevalent building technique in numerous regions across the country. These structures are not exclusive to India; they are widespread globally, particularly in the construction of low-rise residential buildings. In recent times, there has been a revived interest in earth-based construction in India, driven by the growing emphasis on sustainable and eco-friendly building practices. Compared to reinforced concrete and steel, earthen construction is often more cost-effective. However, traditional earthen structures may exhibit insufficient structural resilience, particularly when faced with intense loading scenarios such as earthquakes. Consequently, damages and even collapses of earthen structures are frequently documented in the aftermath of seismic events. To address this issue, various styles of interlocking blocks have been developed with the goal of improving both the efficiency and quality of the construction process as reported in several studies (Xie *et al.* 2022, Shi *et al.* 2021, Jaafar *et al.* 2005). Besides, past studies reported different techniques of seismic strengthening of earthen as well as burnt clay brick masonry houses (Sharma *et al.* 2016, Sharma *et al.* 2015). In fact, studies were more focused through experimental methods and limited numerical analysis was attempted. Hence, present study is motivated to perform numerical analysis in order to save time and cost involved with experiments. In our quest to introduce a sophisticated interlocking block design that enhances structural performance, we have adopted a numerical approach using ABAQUS 6.14 for thorough three dimensional (3D) finite element analysis. The initial phase involves creating detailed 3D models of the interlocking block system within ABAQUS 6.14 as per Xie *et al.* (2022). These models capture the intricacies of the proposed design, including interlocking features, material properties, and geometric complexities. Moving forward, we have conducted a series of simulations within ABAQUS 6.14 to scrutinize how the interlocking block system behaves under various loading conditions. This analysis provides valuable insights into the performance of interlocking block system and identifying potential areas for design improvement.

Modeling and Method of Analysis

Interlocking Block

Fig. 1 presents a detailed depiction of the arrangement of an interlocking block as proposed by Xie *et al.* (2022) each measuring 100 mm in length, 90 mm in height, and 50 mm in thickness. These blocks are characterized by prominent raised grooves, reaching a depth of 30 mm. The blocks are modelled with substantial projections (tenons) and corresponding indentations (mortises) that establish secure connections with neighbouring blocks. This deliberate design significantly bolsters the interlocking wall's capacity to withstand shear forces effectively. This innovative configuration stands in contrast to conventional interlocking blocks available in the market, which typically incorporate small protrusions primarily for alignment purposes rather than robust structural interlocking. The deliberate inclusion of sizable tenons and mortises in our design ensures a robust and dependable interlocking mechanism, setting it apart from other alternatives. It's worth noting that these interlocking blocks are constructed from lateritic soil, imparting them with

traditional brick-like constitutive properties. This material choice not only aligns with established construction practices but also contributes to the overall strength and durability of the interlocking wall system.

Fig.1. Detailing of Interlocking block (a) top view (b) front view (c) back view and (d) left view (after Xie *et al.* (2022)).

Numerical Modeling

In order to gain deeper insights into the behaviour of interlocking blocks and to facilitate more comprehensive research, highly detailed three-dimensional numerical models of these interlocking blocks have been meticulously generated. This process involves utilizing the ABAQUS 6.14 software to model the blocks. To effectively simulate the behaviour of interlocking bricks in the ABAQUS 6.14 environment, a thorough simulation approach is adopted, comprising multiple crucial steps. The initial stage involves creating a precise geometric representation of the 3D structure of the interlocking bricks within the ABAQUS 6.14 environment. To accurately capture the structural intricacies, the element type C3D8R in ABAQUS 6.14, specifically the continuum stress/displacement three-dimensional eight-node reduced-integration hexahedral element, is selected as the solid element for modelling. Following the geometric representation, a meticulous meshing process is employed to discretise the geometry into finite elements. Special attention is dedicated to ensuring that the mesh effectively captures the complexities present in the interlocking regions of the blocks. This comprehensive numerical modelling approach lays the foundation for a detailed and accurate analysis of the interlocking block behaviour, providing valuable insights for further study and exploration in the field.

Material Model

The block material is simulated using the concrete damaged plasticity (cdp) model, a renowned choice for its ability to accurately represent tensile and compressive behaviour in various directions. This model is particularly notable for its incorporation of progressive material damage, making it well-suited for simulating the complex characteristics of materials that exhibit brittle behaviour. Widely adopted for simulating the structural behaviour of concrete and rock, the CDP model has proven effective in capturing the intricate responses of these materials under various loading conditions. A recent study (Shi *et al.* 2021) delving into the effectiveness of interlocking blocks showcased promising results when employing the Concrete Damaged Plasticity model. The model's adaptability and capacity to simulate progressive damage

played a pivotal role in accurately capturing the structural behaviour of interlocking blocks, highlighting its applicability in the analysis and design of such structural elements. The material properties used in this study (Table 1 & 2) has been taken from Xie *et al.* (2022).

Table 1. Material properties used to model the blocks.

Mass density (kg/m ³)	Young's modulus, E_0 (MPa)	Poisson's ratio, ν	Plasticity Dilatation angle, ψ (°)	Eccentricity	Biaxial stress ratio, f_{bo}/f_{co}	K	Viscosity Parameter
2535.32	4000	0.22	12	0.1	1.16	0.66667	0

Note: K represents the ratio between the second stress invariant on the tensile meridian and the compressive meridian at the point of initial yield.

Table 2. Material constants for the CDP model.

Compressive behaviour		Tensile behaviour	
Yield Stress (MPa)	Inelastic strain	Yield stress (MPa)	Cracking strain
1.68	0	0.13	0
2.00	0.00021	0.06	0.00027
1.83	0.00164	0.05	0.0004
1.53	0.00338	0.05	0.00051
1.27	0.00505	0.04	0.00062
1.04	0.00662	0.04	0.00073
0.87	0.00773	0.04	0.00083
0.77	0.00829	0.04	0.00094
0.51	0.00972		
0.34	0.01065		

Model Details

To conduct a thorough numerical analysis, a representative wallet (Fig. 2(a)) is modelled within the ABAQUS 6.14 environment. This involves constraining the axial and horizontal degrees of freedom at the base. To simulate the contact behaviour at the joints of interlocking blocks, a perfect contact modelling method is employed with the help of tie constraint. This method assumes smooth brick surfaces and perfect contact conditions between adjacent blocks, facilitating an accurate representation of forces transferred based on tangential and normal contact behaviour. The loading is applied through the displacement control loading method, utilizing varying displacements of 5, 10, 15, 25, and 30 mm. This approach allows for a comprehensive exploration of the wallet's structural response under different loading conditions. The finite element model is discretised with a hexahedral type of mesh of size 10 mm (Fig. 2(b)). The choice of mesh size is arbitrary and it ensures a fine resolution that effectively captures the intricate details of the interlocking regions. Special attention is given to refining the mesh in critical areas, particularly at the interlocking interfaces.

Results and discussions

Load-displacement curves

In Fig. 3, we observe the load-displacement curve depicting the behaviour of the model wallet when subjected to lateral and vertical displacements. The findings reveal a direct correlation between displacement and load, indicating that as the displacement increases, there is a concurrent rise in the applied load. This observation provides valuable insights into the structural response of the model wallet under different loading conditions.

Fig.2. (a) Interlocking block wallet model, (b) meshed block.

Fig.3. Load-displacement curves under (a) lateral loading and (b) vertical loading.

Conclusions

The study delves into the rich historical context of earthen construction, particularly mud or adobe structures, prevalent in India and globally for low-rise residential buildings. Employing a numerical approach with ABAQUS 6.14, we meticulously simulated a sophisticated interlocking block system which was proposed by Xie *et al.* (2022). Crafted from lateritic soil, these blocks exhibit traditional brick-like properties, contributing to the strength and durability of the interlocking wall system. The adoption of the Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model facilitated accurate representation of material behavior, crucial for understanding structural responses. Numerical simulations explored various loading conditions, evaluating compressive strength, shear resistance, and deformation characteristics. The perfect contact modeling method allowed a detailed examination of joint behavior in interlocking blocks, revealing valuable insights into the system's performance. The analysis of a representative wallet under different loading conditions provided a nuanced understanding, exemplified by the load-displacement curve correlating displacement with maximum load. The findings lay a foundation for design improvements, promising more resilient and sustainable solutions in the realm of earthen construction practices.

References

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